
PEDAGOGICAL ASPECTS OF DEVELOPING CREATIVE SKILLS OF STUDENTS

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Annotatsiya. Ushbu maqolada o‘quv jarayonida pedagog tomonidan pedagogika oliy o‘quv yurti talabalari ijodiy qobiliyatlarini rivojlantirishni ta‘minlanishning modeli va uning asosiy va sistema hosil qiluvchi komponentlari bayon etilgan. Talabalar ijodiy qobiliyatlarini rivojlantirish qonuniyatlari kuchga kirishiga olib keladigan asosiy pedagogik omillarga to‘xtalgan.

Kalit so‘zlar: determinatsiya, genetik, genotip, pedagogik ijod, ijodiy faoliyat, gnoseologik fenomen, pedagogik qonuniyat, pedagogik prinsip, muammoli vaziyat, intellektual malakalar.

ПЕДАГОГИЧЕСКИЕ АСПЕКТЫ РАЗВИТИЯ ТВОРЧЕСКИХ НАВЫКОВ СТУДЕНТОВ

Абстрактный: В данной статье описана модель обеспечения развития творческих способностей студентов педагогического вуза педагогом в ходе образовательного процесса и ее основные и системообразующие компоненты. Он коснулся основных педагогических факторов, которые приводят к реализации закономерностей развития творческих способностей учащихся.

Ключевые слова: детерминация, генетика, генотип, педагогическое творчество, творческая деятельность, гнесеологический феномен, педагогическая легитимность, педагогический принцип, проблемная ситуация, интеллектуальные.

PEDAGOGICAL ASPECTS OF DEVELOPING CREATIVE SKILLS OF STUDENTS

Abstract. In this article, the model of ensuring the development of creative abilities of students of the pedagogical university by the pedagogue during the educational process and its main and system-forming components are described. He touched on the main pedagogical factors that lead to the implementation of the laws of the development of students' creative abilities.

Key words: determination, genetic, genotype, pedagogical creativity, creative activity, epistemological phenomenon, pedagogical legitimacy, pedagogical principle, problem situation, intellectual skills.

The following complex of pedagogical conditions ensures the effectiveness of the development of creative abilities of students of pedagogy OO'YU in educational activities:

motivational conditions: justification of the place and role of creativity in the professional activity of the pedagogue; realizing that new opportunities for solving problems will appear;

constructive conditions: providing students with knowledge about the mechanisms of creative activity; inclusion of creative tasks in the educational content; appropriate methodological support;

organizational conditions: use of methods and forms of organizing educational and creative activities; use of group and individual forms of educational organization;

communicative conditions: the teacher's communicative culture is formed at a very high level; using dialogue as subject-subject mutual cooperation of teacher and students.

The final result of the application of the developed model to educational activities is to increase the quality of the teacher's professional training based on the development of creative abilities. At the modern stage of the development of our society, the requirements for the professional creative level of specialists, the latest achievements of science and the shortening of the production and application of advanced technologies to the social sphere are increasing.

Today, higher educational institutions will be able to find their place in life, promising, ready to creatively implement their professional activities, that is, they will be able not only to solve sufficiently complex tasks, but also to advance problems, to find fundamentally new creative solutions. the task of developing a specialist is set.

In psychology, there are three complementary approaches to explaining the ways of personality development:

1) an approach that allocates the main role to heredity in the determination of genetic and mental characteristics;

2) environmental, its representatives consider external conditions to be the decisive factor in the development of psychic abilities;

3) genotype-environment interaction, proponents of this approach distinguish between different types of adaptation of an individual to the environment depending on hereditary aspects.

The model we have developed for the development of creative abilities of pedagogic OOUUU students in the educational process includes a number of interrelated components.

One of the main and system-forming components of the model is the target component. Based on the purpose of our research, the goal of the studied system is to improve the process of developing the creative abilities of students of pedagogic OOUUU.

For the successful realization of the set goal, it is necessary to solve the following tasks:

- arming students with knowledge about creativity, pedagogical creativity, mechanisms of creative activity;
- forming a positive attitude to creative activity in future teachers;
- formation of personal qualities, as well as skills, necessary to carry out activities at a creative level.

In the development of the theoretical methodological component of the system, we were based on pedagogical factors, laws, principles of organizing the pedagogical process.

It is known that the pedagogical factor is the driving force of any pedagogical process. In the realization of concrete factors in the process of education and training, a certain lawfulness of changing the direction and nature of teaching and learning activities, and ultimately the results of the educational process, is manifested by objective necessity. Determining laws is one of the main tasks of any scientific theory.

The laws of the pedagogical process include the basic requirements for the organization of pedagogical activities; it finds its concrete expression in the rules of leadership, i.e. principles, which show its direction. Laws exist objectively, and principles are an epistemological phenomenon that reflects the essence of law in a normative form. That is, pedagogical law and pedagogical principle are considered as "existing" and "necessary".

Based on the analysis of literary sources and pedagogical work experience, we focused on the group of main pedagogical factors that lead to the implementation of the laws of development of creative abilities of learners. Identified laws make it possible to form the principles of organizing pedagogical activities that help students to develop their creative abilities.

Factor 1. Creative nature of educational activity.

Creative abilities are necessary for creative activity, but S. L. Rubinstein said: "In the activities that a person performs and can accomplish in his life, all the psychic characteristics of a person are not only manifested, but also formed."

Abilities are formed in the process of interaction of a person with one or another quality with the world.

Summarizing the results of human activity, "building material" is included in the construction of its abilities. Therefore, the factor of ensuring the creative nature of educational activity should be the main one. Leading researchers say so.

It can be argued that creative activity creates conditions for the development of creative abilities. The procedural side of creative activity consists in finding and solving a problem. When it comes to teaching, we need to clarify what we mean by the term educational problem.

However, not every task can be a learning problem. A learning problem is a reflection of the logical-psychological contradiction of the process of mastering, which determines the direction of intellectual research, arouses interest in researching (explaining) the essence of the unknown, and leads to the clarification of a new concept or method of action. (to appear) is understood"

1. Andriadi I.P. Osnovi pedagogicheskogo masterstva: Ucheb. allowance for stud. average ped. ucheb zadaniy. M.: Izdatelsky Center "Academy", 1999.-160 p.

In problematic teaching conditions, great importance is attached to creating a problem situation. It can occur in the process of solving the educational problem before it is formed. Psychologists and pedagogues define the nature of the problematic situation differently, but both sides show certain signs that are characteristic of it. These are: 1) a state of intellectual difficulty arises; 2) a conflict situation arises; 3) the student's knowledge and skills needed to understand, explain, and solve the problem are not compatible.

There are known ways to create a problematic situation:

choice, decision, creating a situation;

fact, comparison of events, comparison;

excursions to the history of discoveries, inventions. Offer to determine cause-and-effect relationships and relationships between events and processes;

to demonstrate methods and facts that show inconsistencies between the theory and the student's life experience;

a fundamentally new look at an ordinary phenomenon;

comparing two or more approaches to explaining the same phenomenon;

experiment from the point of view of different sciences, put questions that require explanation.

Factor 2. Acquisition of necessary knowledge and skills for creative activity. The creative skills that affect the development of creative abilities that we are studying belong to the highest level of this hierarchy. This is the total (sum) of skills that provide a direct creative process within this specialization. These skills, first of all, are related to the nature of the main psychological processes and their increasingly general laws, which are usually outside the scope of professional activity. What we are studying is a generalization of the correspondence between creative abilities and the necessary skills for their development.

Creative skills, Creative skills, Problem vision

Determining relative oppositions, asking problematic questions, separating the task from the background, looking for other ways of representing the problem, dividing into small problems

Completeness of perception

To see the connections and relations of the object, to see the structure of the object, to distinguish between serious and non-serious signs of an object (event), to see serious common aspects in different objects (events), to see serious features in very similar objects (events) see the difference

Readiness of memory means systematization of knowledge, filling and reconstruction of knowledge system (dynamics of knowledge), transfer of knowledge to new situations. Abstraction (abstraction), search for analogies, evaluation of known methods of knowledge and action in relation to existing conditions, easy association and comparison of imaginary objects with elements of detailing, comparison of the object as part of the whole, "direct" comparisons based on comparison of incompatible elements, to identify relationships by kind, to imagine objects in a different way; creating new images by agglutination.

Subtle thinking, moving to another idea, changing the usual time relations, changing the usual space relations, changing the usual generality relations.

Dialectics of thinking, determination of oppositional relations, dialectical unification, dialectical mediation, dialectical appeal, dialectical conversion.

Originality of thinking, abandonment of a certain method or theory, use of by-products of activity.

Forecasting (forecasting) is the implementation of prospective planning, predicting the results of each step of the decision.

The criticality of thinking is the choice of criteria for evaluating the idea, the analysis of ideas from the point of view of the criteria, the choice of the optimal decision idea.

Separate creative skills are necessary for the practical realization of the mechanisms of creative activity, and some of them are completely compatible with heuristics in definition, which emphasizes their interdependence. Competencies that

guarantee the success of actions in accordance with the goals and tasks of the activity are considered to be formed. Different stages of skill formation are distinguished in psychological-pedagogical literature. Intellectual skills are more closely related to creative skills. They also belong to (according to the classification of A.V. Usova) knowledge and (according to the classification of R.F. Krivoshanova) interdisciplinary skills.

Factor 3. Taking into account the achieved level of creative abilities, taking into account the individual characteristics of learners in all its forms and methods in the educational process, regardless of what features and to what extent, is called individualization of education.

Therefore, it is necessary to determine the level of development of each student, it is not allowed to level the levels of development, that is, individualization is maintained throughout the entire period of education; developmental tasks should be of optimal complexity. All these conclusions can be made in relation to the development of creative abilities.

On this basis, the following law can be formulated: the development of creative abilities depends on the individual characteristics of students, their level of manifestation. This law is implemented through the principle of individualization based on the level of development of creative abilities. Usova A.V. Formirovaniye u uchashikhsya obshikh uchebno-poznavatelinkh umeniy v protsesse izucheniya zadamen yesestvennogo sikla. — Chelyabinsk, 1997.-178 p. Anastazi A. Psikhologicheskoye testirovaniye. V 2-x t. T.1. M.: Pedagogy, 1982. - 318 p.

Factor 4. Stimulator and manager of a person's creative activity.

It is known in psychology that a person develops as a whole. "The essence of cultural development is that a person acquires his own behavioral processes, but the necessary factor for this is the presence of a person, therefore the development of this or that function is a product of the general development of the person and is determined by it", therefore the process of developing creative abilities we cannot study it in isolation from the main parts of the creative person. The following law follows from what has been said: the development of creative abilities is encouraged and controlled by other components of a creative person. The following complex of pedagogical conditions ensures the effectiveness of the development of creative abilities of students of pedagogy OO'YU in educational activities:

motivational conditions: justification of the place and role of creativity in the professional activity of the pedagogue; realizing that new opportunities for solving problems will appear;

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organizational conditions: use of methods and forms of organizing educational and creative activities; use of group and individual forms of educational organization; communicative conditions: the teacher's communicative culture is formed at a very high level; using dialogue as subject-subject mutual cooperation of teacher and students.

The final result of the application of the developed model to educational activities is to increase the quality of the teacher's professional training based on the development of creative abilities.

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